

Synthesis and Reactions of 3-Halo-1,8-naphthyridin-2,4-diones

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Naphthyridinones, a class of compounds possessing a wide spectrum of medicinal properties, have been studied for activity against various organisms¹. This prompted us to prepare some new members of this class of compounds.

The starting material (1), prepared by fusion of 2-aminopyridine with diethylmalonate², was subjected to various halogenating agents. Characterisation of the products revealed that halogenation took place at positions 3, 4 and/or 6.

Thus compound 1 was reacted with sulphuryl chloride to produce 3,3-dichloro-1,8-naphthyridin-2,4-dione (2). Where 1 in dioxane medium may be present in the dione form (1') having active methylene group at position-3, which is capable to substitute its two protons by two chlorine atoms when reacted with sulphuryl chloride. Chlorination took place mainly at the methylene group rather than at the aromatic ring, since SO₂Cl₂ is specific for methylene group^{3,4}. On the other hand, phosphorus oxychloride produced 4-chloro-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one (3).

Substitution of one hydrogen atom at position-3 by a bromine atom was effected by the action of bromine on a solution of 1 in formic acid, affording 3-bromo-4-hydroxy-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one (4). But when bromination was carried out in dioxane medium using HBr-Br₂ as the brominating agent, the substitution took place at both the positions 3 and 6 to produce 3,6-dibromo-4-hydroxy-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one (5). On the other

hand, both the hydrogens at position-3 of the starting material (having the form 1' in dioxane solution) were substituted by two bromine atoms, when 1 was reacted for a short time period and at low temperature (35°) with bromine in dioxane, giving 3,3-dibromo-1,8-naphthyridin-2,4-dione (6). When this reaction was conducted at the boiling point of the reaction-mixture and for a longer time period, a third bromine atom substituted the hydrogen at position-6 yielding 3,3,6-tribromo-1,8-naphthyridin-2,4-dione (7). Compound 7 was also obtained by reacting 3-formyl-4-hydroxy-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one (8)² with HBr-H₂O₂ in boiling dioxane (Scheme 1).

Interconversion of the bromo derivatives (4-7) were carried out by further bromination under different conditions or by reduction. Thus the 3,6-dibromo derivatives (5) was obtained when the 3-monobromo derivative (4) was further brominated with Br₂-HBr in boiling dioxane and/or reduction of the 3,3,6-tribromo derivative (7), while the 3,3-dibromo compound (6) was produced by warming 4 with bromine in aqueous dioxane. On the other hand, 6 was converted to 4 by reduction using Zn/AcOH. Moreover, 7 was obtained by boiling either 4 or 5 with bromine in aqueous dioxane.

Iodination of the starting material (1) by treatment with a solution of iodine in dioxane in presence of sodium carbonate gave rise to substitution of one hydrogen atom at position-3 by an iodine atom to produce 4-hydroxy-3-iodo-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one (9).

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) SO_2Cl_2 , (ii) POCl_3 , (iii) $\text{Br}_2\text{-HCO}_2\text{H}$, (iv) $\text{Br}_2/\text{HBr-dioxane}$, (v) $\text{Br}_2\text{-aqueous dioxane}$, (vi) $\text{HBr}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2\text{-dioxane}$, (vii) Zn/AcOH , (viii) DMF/POCl_3 .

The 3,3-dihalo derivatives (2 and 6) were used as starting materials for the synthesis of some new naphthyridinones of the expected biological activity. These reactions reveal that the two chlorine atoms in 2 or the two bromine atoms of 6 are present at position-3, since both 2 and 6 were converted to one and the same product².

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP3-300 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (DMSO-d_6) on a Varian EM 360 (60 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. 4-Hydroxy-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one was synthesised according to the reported method².

4-Hydroxy-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one (1) : A mixture of an equimolar amounts of 2-aminopyridine and diethylmalonate was refluxed for 6 h. The crystalline solid formed upon cooling was crystallised from water (85%), m.p. 292–94°.

3,3-Dichloro-1,8-naphthyridin-2,4-dione (2) : To a warm (50°) suspension of 1 (4 g) in dioxane (10 ml), sulphuryl chloride (5.5 ml) was added slowly with stirring. The reaction mixture was boiled for 15 min, then cooled and diluted with ice-cold water (30 ml). The resulting solid was crystallised from benzene (43%), m.p. 149°.

4-Chloro-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one (3) : A mixture of 1 (1 g) and phosphorus oxychloride (3 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 30 min. The reaction mixture was then poured onto crushed ice and extracted with chloroform. The solid obtained after evaporation of chloroform, was crystallised (30%), m.p. 185°.

3-Bromo-4-hydroxy-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one (4) : To 4-hydroxy-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one 1 (1 g) dissolved in hot formic acid (20 ml), excess bromine (1 ml) was added and the mixture was left at room temperature for 4 h. It was then neutralised by dilute sodium carbonate, and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from water, (64%), m.p. 120°.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)	δ
1	3 300 (NH, naphthyridinone), 3 050, 3 010 (Ar, olifinic C-H), 2 500 (br, H-bonded OH), 1 680, 1 640 (C=O at position-2, -4, tautomeric), 1 500-1 620 (ring vib.)	9.6 (1H, br, OH), 8.9-9.1 (1H, br, NH), 7.3-8.2 (3H, m, ArH), 5.2 (1H, s, CH at position-3)
2	3 300 (N-H, naphthyridinone), 3 090, 3 010 (Ar, CH), 1 670, 1 630 (C=O at positions-4, -2)	-
3	3 380 (br, H-bonded N-H), 3 020, 3 010 (Ar, olifinic C-H), 1 710 (C=O at position-2)	-
4	3 400 (N-H), 3 100, 3 010 (Ar. C-H), 2 800 (br, OH at position- 4), 1 625 (C=O at position-2)	-
5	3 290 (N-H), 3 090 (Ar. C-H), 2 650 (br, H-boded O-H), 1 670 (C=O at position-2)	-
6	3 260 (N-H), 3 090 (Ar. C-H), 1 680, 1 640 (C=O at position-4, -2)	8.3 (1H, s, NH), 7-8 (3H, m, Ar)
7	3 350 (N-H), 3 090 (Ar. C-H), 1 695, 1 640 (C=O at position-4, -2)	-
9	3 480 (N-H), 3 090 (Ar. C-H), 2 800 (br, H-bonded O-H), 1 1 625 (C=O at position-2)	-

* All compounds gave satisfactory, C, H and N analyses; in addition 2--7,9 satisfactory halogen analysis.

3,6-Dibromo-4-hydroxy-1,8-naphthyridin-2-dione (5) : A mixture of **1** (3.2 g), dioxane (12 ml) and concentrated HBr (5 ml) was boiled. Bromine was then added dropwise until its colour persisted in the solution. It was then refluxed for 15 min, diluted with water, neutralised with sodium carbonate and the resulting solid crystallised from water, (25%), m.p. 95°.

3,3-Dibromo-1,8-naphthyridin-2,4-dione (6) : A mixture of **1** (1 g), dioxane (10 ml), water (5 ml) and bromine (0.6 ml) was warmed to 35° for 5 min and then diluted with water. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from cyclohexane, (80%), m.p. 242-44°.

3,3,6-Tribromo-1,8-naphthyridin-2,4-dione (7) : (a) To a solution of **1** (5 g) in dioxane (30

ml) and water (15 ml), bromine (3.9 ml) was added dropwise at 25°. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 10 min, cooled and diluted with 55 ml water. The solid formed was crystallised from dioxane (70%), m.p. 233-35°. (b) A mixture of 3-formyl-4-hydroxy-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one (**8**^{2,3}; 1 g), dioxane (15 ml), concentrated HBr (5 ml) and H₂O₂ (20 ml; 30°), was warmed and then cooled. The yellow crystals formed was crystallised from dioxane to give **7** (25%; m.p. and m.m.p.).

Interconversion of the bromo derivatives :
Conversion of 4 to 5 : A mixture of **4** (0.1 mol), bromine (0.1 mol), HBr (5 ml) and dioxane (20 ml) was boiled for 10 min, then cooled, diluted with water to afford **5** (m.p. and m.m.p.).

Reduction of the bromo compounds containing two bromine atoms at position-3 (6 and 7).
General method :

Conversion of 6 to 4, and 7 to 5 : To a solution of either **6** or **7** (0.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml), zinc dust (0.1 g) was added, and the reaction mixture was warmed and left to cool. The colourless crystalline product deposited was found to be identical with **4** or **5** respectively (m.p., m.m.p. and spectra).

Conversion of 4 to 6 : Compound **4** (0.1 mol) in aqueous dioxane (10 ml; 50%) was treated with bromine (0.1 mol) at 35°, then cooled and diluted with water. The resulting solid was crystallised from cyclohexane to afford **6** (m.p., m.m.p. and spectra).

Conversion of 6 to 7 : A mixture of **6** (0.1 mol), Br₂ and aqueous dioxane (20 ml; 50%) was refluxed for 30 min, then cooled. The solid formed was crystallised from dioxane to give compound **7** (m.p. and m.m.p.).

Conversion of 4 to 7 : To a mixture of **4** (0.1 mol), aqueous dioxane (10 ml), bromine (0.2 mol) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 0.5 h. The solid formed upon cooling was crystallised from dioxane to give **7** (m.p. and m.m.p.).

Conversion of 5 to 7 : To a suspension of **5** (0.1 mol) in aqueous dioxane (10 ml, 50%), bromine (0.1 mol) was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 15 min and then cooled. The solid formed was crystallised from dioxane to give (m.p. and m.m.p.).

4-Hydroxy-3-iodo-1,8-naphthyridin-2-one (9) : Compound **1** (2 g) was dissolved in a solution of sodium carbonate [(2.5 g) in water (50 ml)], then boiled and treated with a solution of iodine (3.5 g) in dioxane (20 ml) till permanent iodine colour persisted. The reaction mixture was then cooled to 5°, neutralised with glacial acetic acid and the resulting solid was washed with methanol and crystallised from water, (73%), m.p. 220–22°.

References

1. H. EGAWA, J. MIYAMOTO, A. MINAMIDA, Y. NIASHIMURA, H. OKADA, H. UNO AND J. MATSUMOTO, *J. Med. Chem.*,

1984, **27**, 1543; K. GROHE, H. J. ZEILER and K. G. METZGER, Ger. Pat. 3 409 922/1985 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, 88589); D. J. CHU, Eur. Pat. 153 580/1985 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, 88585); D. J. CHU, Eur. Pat. 227 088/1987 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, 217616); A. A. SANTILLI, A. C. SCOTSE, R. F. BAUER and S. C. BELL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1987, **30**, 2270; M. H. SHERLOK, J. J. KAMINSKI, W. C. TOM, J. F. LEE, S. WONG, W. KREUTNER, R. W. BRYANT and A. T. MCPHAIL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1988, **31**, 2108; H. GRAF, L. FRANZ, H. SAUTER, E. AMMERMANN and E. H. POMMER, Ger Pat. 3 644 825/1988 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, 170409); J. M. DOMAGALA and P. PEATERSON. *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1989, **26**, 1147.

2. E. A. MOHAMED, R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN, Z. EL-GENDY and M. M. ISMAIL, *An. Quim Real Soc. Espanola Quim.*, 1993, **89**, 246.
3. E. ZIEGLER, L. F. WERNER and T. KAPPE, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1969, **100**, 610.
4. E. A. BADAWAY, S. M. RIDA, F. S. SOLIMAN and T. KAPPE, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1989, **120** 1159.